

ISic3517

I.Sicily inscription 3517

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

, sep.115

Coordinates

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3569

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus)
2. M(arcus) U(lpius) Euty
3. c[he]s s[ib]i e[re]t col
4. libertis suis ·
5. fecit ·

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1916 (text and drawing) and Bitto, with modifications

Orsi: M. Ulpius | Euty

Orsi: c[h]es [Sib] Et con

Translation

Commentary

Inscription on one face of a tabula (broken) and this probably the more recent inscription of the two. Misreported by Bitto (I.Messina I), under her no.v, as being from the same tomb as ISic3323, which it is not (see Orsi). Only the lower

half (lines 4-5) survives now in the museum at Messina, but Orsi made a clear drawing of the whole.

Digital identifiers:

TM 284784

EDR 100006

PHI 313634

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 8

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 147 fig.19

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 50

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